

Synthesis of CdWO₄ nanoparticles by co-precipitation method

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Abstract:

Transition metal tungstates of M²⁺WO₄ type (M²⁺ = Co, Cu, Cd, Mn, Pb and Zn) are ternary oxide semiconductors that are attracting considerable attention because they exhibit interesting technological properties such as ferroelasticity, ionic conductivity, and photoluminescence. Cadmium tungstate (CdWO₄) with a monoclinic wolframite structure belongs to the important family of metal tungstates. The present work report the synthesis of CdWO₄ nanoparticles using Co-precipitation method. The chemicals used for the synthesis of CdWO₄ nanoparticles were sodium tungstate and cadmium acetate. The synthesised white powder was calcined at 500°C for 2 hrs. The synthesized sample was investigated by XRD, FT-IR, UV-Vis, PL and SEM-EDX to identify its various properties. The XRD analysis confirmed the formation of monoclinic structure of CdWO₄. The band gap value of CdWO₄ was found to be 3.07 eV using Tauc's plot. The EDX study proved the purity of synthesized product.

Keywords: Metal tungstate, CdWO₄, monoclinic wolframite structure

References

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